

Chemical Implication of Copper-Molybdenum Antagonism. Solubilisation of Copper Sulphide with Tetrathiomolybdate(VI) Anion to isolate Discrete Cu-S-Mo Compounds

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Freshly precipitated CuS can be solubilised with MoS_4^{2-} in aqueous medium on standing and discrete compounds $[(\text{PPh}_3)_3\text{Cu}_2\text{MoS}_4]$ and $[(o\text{-phen})_2\text{Cu}_2\text{MoS}_4]$ were isolated. The reaction has been carried out to mimic a feasible reaction which may occur in the rumen and the chemical implications of copper-molybdenum antagonism has been rationalised. The solubilisation of CuS with MoS_4^{2-} has been proposed to be responsible for the resorption stage of the interaction.

THE chemical implication of Cu-Mo antagonism is one of the intense current interests to chemists, biochemists and those involved in the agricultural aspects of ruminant animals¹. MoS_4^{2-} has been proved to be the greatest antagonist of copper and a very insoluble species of the composition protein-Cu-MoS₄ has been proposed to be responsible for the clinical and bio-chemical deficiency of copper in ruminants². Hence, the synthesis of models compounds having protein-Cu-MoS₄ system may shed some light on the chemical implications of the phenomenon. Thus, several model compounds having similar heterometal core have been synthesised³ but in all these compounds Cu is flanked by P-donor ligands which cannot be taken as representatives of proteins because P is not a potential donor site in proteins. Instead, Cu-MoS₄²⁻ heterometal system in which Cu is flanked by N, S or O donor ligands may be considered as models for protein-Cu-MoS₄ systems because N, S and O are the potential donor sites in proteins. No such system has yet been reported in literature. Moreover, the heterometal systems reported³ so far have all been synthesised in non-aqueous medium but the Cu-Mo interaction taking place in the rumen occurs in aqueous medium. We wish to report herein the reaction of CuS and MoS_4^{2-} in aqueous medium to generate discrete Cu-MoS₄ compounds in which copper is flanked by N-donor ligand *o*-phenanthroline and hence, may be taken as representatives of protein-Cu-MoS₄ system.

Also, the conclusion that MoS_4^{2-} is formed from MoO_4^{2-} within S^{2-} rich environment of the rumen does not take into account the presence of copper ions in that environment before an antagonistic interaction between MoS_4^{2-} and copper ions^{4,5} occurs. But from the solubility product principle, it is Cu^{2+} ion which should interact with S^{2-} in preference to MoO_4^{2-} and hence, CuS will be precipitated first before the formation of MoS_4^{2-} (Ref. 6). It might be thought, therefore, that although CuS

is very insoluble in nature, it may respond to copper metabolism, and its further reaction with MoS_4^{2-} leads to the formation of Cu-MoS₄²⁻ aggregates responsible for Cu-Mo antagonism. The demonstration of solubilisation of CuS in MoS_4^{2-} in the following experiment carried out in aqueous medium and the isolation of discrete N-donor-Cu-MoS₄²⁻ systems is certainly of potential biochemical relevance regarding the antagonistic interaction between Cu^{2+} and MoS_4^{2-} .

Experimental

All reagents used were reagent grade. IR spectra were recorded in a Perkin-Elmer 580B spectrometer in CsI disc. Electronic and reflectance spectra were recorded using a Cary 17D spectrophotometer. Raman and resonance Raman spectra were recorded using a Coderg T800 three-fold monochromator and with a Spex Raman log V two-fold monochromator; energy source Kr⁺ laser (coherent 500 K, 647.1 nm) and for resonance Raman, Ar⁺ laser (Coherent CR4, 488 nm). X-Ray photoelectron spectra were measured by Vacuum Generators ESCALAB 510 photoelectron spectrophotometer; Al-K_α X-Ray line (1 486.6 eV) radiation was used.

Freshly precipitated CuS was added to an aqueous solution of MoS_4^{2-} in 1:1, 2:1, 3:1 and 4:1 ratios and kept for 16 h, whereby in all four sets, a red solution was obtained indicating the dissolution of CuS in MoS_4^{2-} . The solutions were filtered and divided into two parts, A and B. Part A-s were treated with triphenylphosphine (in DMF), and part B-s were treated with *o*-phenanthroline (in DMF). Again in all the four sets, the compound $[(\text{PPh}_3)_3\text{Cu}_2\text{MoS}_4]^+$ was obtained from Part A-s, and $[(o\text{-phen})_2\text{Cu}_2\text{MoS}_4]^+$ from Part B-s indicating the existence of only one type of core, $\{\text{Cu}_2\text{MoS}_4\}$, in all four sets of the red solutions.

To demonstrate the 'spontaneous self assembly' of $\{Cu_2MoS_4\}$ core and also the *in situ* generation and interaction of CuS and MoS_4^{2-} which probably may occur in ruminants, $Cu^{2+}/MoO_4^{2-}/H_2S$ system was also studied with varying ratios of Cu^{2+} and MoO_4^{2-} , i.e. 1 : 1, 2 : 1, 3 : 1 and 4 : 1. A typical experiment is described below.

$(NH_4)_6Mo_7O_{24} \cdot 24H_2O$ (0.55 g, 0.5 mmol) and $CuCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ (1.2 g, 7 mmol) were dissolved in a mixture (60 ml) of water (15 ml) and ammonia (50 ml, sp. gr.=0.9). A continuous current of H_2S was passed into the solution. CuS was precipitated immediately and stepwise replacement of oxo group of MoO_4^{2-} by S^{2-} resulted in the ultimate formation of MoS_4^{2-} when the passage of H_2S was stopped (45 min)⁹. The contents were kept for 16 h whereby most of the precipitated CuS went into the solution¹⁰. The resultant solution was filtered and divided into two parts (Part A and Part B).

Part A was poured into a solution of triphenylphosphine (0.65 g, 10.5 mmol) in DMF (30 ml) whereby a red microcrystalline compound separated out. It was filtered, washed with acetone, carbon disulphide and ether and vacuum dried¹¹. The compound was characterised as $[(PPh_3)_2Cu_2MoS_4]$, which had earlier been synthesised and structurally characterised in non-aqueous medium⁷. The salient feature of the structure of this known complex is the unsymmetrical environment of copper centres where one of the copper is tetrahedrally coordinated (two PPh_3 and two S centres of MoS_4^{2-}) whereas the other copper has a triangular planar environment (one PPh_3 and the remaining two S centres of MoS_4^{2-}). It is noteworthy to mention that attempts to synthesise similar compound with tetrahedral environment around both copper centres have failed although symmetrical environment around Ag centres could be obtained in the compound $[(PPh_3)_4Ag_2MoS_4]^{12}$.

Part B was poured into a solution of *o*-phenanthroline (1.4 g, 7 mmol) in DMF (30 ml). Addition of acetone (20 ml) resulted in the precipitation of a red compound which was filtered, washed with acetone, carbon disulphide and ether and vacuum dried. Analysis and spectroscopic results suggest it to be $[(o\text{-phen})_2Cu_2MoS_4]^8$. Thus, we could achieve a tetrahedral environment around both copper centres.

Discussion

It has now been demonstrated that discrete Cu-S-Mo compounds flanked by N-donors can be isolated from aqueous solution which may serve as an appropriate model for Cu-Mo antagonism demonstrating the interaction between protein moiety and the heterometal core comprising of Cu and Mo^{2+} .

core, isolated from the reaction mixture, contains

Cu and Mo in the ratio 2 : 1, and recently in an *in vivo* experiment, the ratio of Cu and Mo were found to be in the same ratio in plasma¹³. Also, the isolated complexes are stable even in acidic medium (upto pH 2) which justifies that within the slightly acidic milieu of the stomach these type of derivatives are stable and remain unabsorbable. The inability of MoO_4^{2-} and $MoOS_3^-$ to inhibit copper absorption as demonstrated recently¹³ may thus be attributed to (i) the difference in the ratios of Cu and Mo in the complexes of MoO_4^{2-} and $MoOS_3^-$ being different^{5,14} from the ratio found in plasma copper¹³ and (ii) the instability of such aggregates in acidic medium due to high proton affinity of oxygen since in all these mixed oxothioanions, copper binds to molybdenum invariably *via* sulphur leaving oxygens attached to molybdenum free^{5,14}.

A parallel attempt to solubilise CuS in WS_4^{2-} using an identical procedure failed which reflects the specific physiological role of molybdenum in such interactions¹⁵. Recently, a difference in the chemical behaviour of MoO_4^{2-} and WO_4^{2-} have been observed in an *in vivo* experiment⁴ also.

The solubility criterion of CuS in MoS_4^{2-} thus suggests a more plausible way of the formation of Cu-S-Mo systems responsible for Cu-Mo antagonism by resorption of CuS and MoS_4^{2-} simultaneously, rather than the isolated resorption of only MoS_4^{2-} followed by its interaction with tissue copper as proposed earlier².

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References

1. It is a phenomenon which occurs in ruminants due to excess uptake of molybdenum and results in the depletion of copper for physiological purposes causing thereby various metabolic disorders (S. SARKAR and S. B. S. MISHRA, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1984, **59**, 299).
2. C. F. MILLS, *Philos. Trans. R. Soc. London, Ser. B*, 1979, **288**, 51.
3. A. MULLER, E. DIEMANN, R. JOSTES and H. BOGGE, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1981, **20**, 934. Also, the necessity of P-donor ligands for the formation of Cu-S-Mo system has been doubted recently (A. MULLER, M. DARTMANN, C. ROMER, W. CLOGG and G. M. SHELDRIK, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1981, **20**, 1060).
4. B. W. YOUNG, I. BREMNER and C. F. MILLS, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 1982, **16**, 121.
5. A. T. DICK, D. W. DEWEY and J. M. GAWTHORNE, *J. Agric. Sci.*, 1975, **85**, 567; C. F. MILLS, I. BREMNER, T. T. EL-GALLAD, A. C. DALGARNO and B. W. YOUNG in "Trace Element Metabolism in Man and Animals", ed. M. KIRCHGESSNER, Vol. 3, Arbeitsgemeinschaft fur Tierernahrungsforschung Friesing-Weihenstephan, 1978, p. 150.
6. An early proposal of formation of CuS was made for physiological non-availability of copper but it made no allowance for interaction with molybdenum (J. HUISINGH, G. G. GOMEZ and G. MATRONE, *Fed. Prog. Fed. Am. Soc. Exp. Biol.*, 1973, **32**, 1921).

7. (Found C, 57.10; H, 3.85; P, 8.02; Cu, 11.20; Mo, 8.32; S, 11.40. $C_{24}H_{12}P_2Cu_2MoS_4$ calcd. for: C, 56.99; H, 3.96; P, 8.17; Cu, 11.17; Mo, 8.44; S, 11.25%). ν_{Mo-S} 465 cm^{-1} ; Raman ν_s (Mo-S) 450 and ν_{as} (Mo-S) 472 cm^{-1} . Also, the X-ray powder diffraction pattern of this compound matched with that of the authentic compound prepared by the established method (A. MULLER, H. BOGGE, H.-C. TOLLE, R. JOSTES, U. SCHIMANSKI and M. DARTMANN, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1980, 19, 654; A. MULLER, H. BOGGE and U. SCHIMANSKI, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1980, 45, L249).
8. (Found C, 39.95; H, 2.35; N, 8.02; Cu, 17.80; Mo, 13.76; S, 18.34. $C_{24}H_{12}N_2Cu_2MoS_4$ calcd. for: C, 40.51; H, 2.25; N, 7.88; Cu, 17.86; Mo, 13.50; S, 18.0%). ν_{Mo-S} 460 cm^{-1} ; Raman ν_s (Mo-S) 441, ν_{as} (Mo-S) 458, ν_{Cu-S} 258, ν_{MoS_4} 161 cm^{-1} . The symmetrical CuS_2MoS_4Cu core was characterised by resonance Raman spectrum (S. SARKAR and S. B. S. MISHRA in "Proceedings Third Symposium on Lasers and Applications", eds. H. D. BIST and J. S. GORLA, Tata McGraw-Hill, 1984, p. 343); XPS data: Cu ($2p_{3/2}$), 933.3; Mo ($3p_{3/2}$), 395.6; Mo($3d_{5/2}$), 229.7; Mo($3d_{3/2}$), 232.8; S ($2p$), 161.6; N($1s$), 399.4; and S($2s$), 225.8 eV (standard: C($1s$), 285.0 eV).
9. Without copper a 30 min passage of H_2S is enough to transform MoO_4^{2-} to MoS_4^{2-} (monitored by 467 nm peak in the electronic spectra).
10. It is interesting because normally, Cu^{2+} immediately reacts with MoS_4^{2-} to precipitate the polymeric $NH_4[CuMoS_4]$, wherein Cu^{2+} is reduced to Cu^+ (W. P. BINNIE, M. J. RIDMAN and W. J. MALLO, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1970, 9, 1449).
11. A further crop of the same compound could be obtained from the mother liquor by acetone precipitation.
12. A. MULLER, H. BOGGE, H. G. TOLLE, R. JOSTES, U. SCHIMANSKI and M. DARTMANN, *Angew. Chem.*, 1980, 92, 665. A symmetrical core around both copper centres could be achieved recently by using thiol as ligand and that too in non-aqueous medium (S. R. ACOTT, C. D. GARNER, J. R. NICHOLSON and W. CLERG, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1983, 713).
13. I. BREMNER, C. F. MILLS and B. W. YOUNG, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 1982, 16, 109.
14. S. B. S. MISHRA, Ph. D. Thesis, IIT-Kanpur, 1983.
15. The solubilisation of CuS with MoS_4^{2-} must have involved concomitant redox processes wherein Cu^{2+} is reduced to Cu^+ . MoS_4^{2-} itself undergoes intra-molecular redox reactions to give several polythioanions in basic medium, whereas the corresponding reactions with WS_4^{2-} are not known (Ref. 3).